

NOVEL APPROACH TO AQUATIC BODIES LOCOMOTION AND REVIEW OF CURRENT STATE: PART 2

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ABSTRACT

The fish locomotion has received enormous amount of attention and yet, as writing this paper, the current status is really poor. In this paper, the rule of thumb for fish was established for the first time. It was found that the tail flexibility has exponential effect on the fish propulsion while the tail height effect is a change from R^3 to R^4 .

The prevailing main model for the fish locomotion partially violates the first and the second thermodynamics laws. To today the real progress is very minimal like the measurement of the movement of the gravity centroid. With so little progress and so much work (grants) one can wonder what is the source for this “science.” The most used model is the fish propelled by the rearrangement of the von Karman vortex street. The errors by the main model were explained in the first installment (Bar-Meir 2022a). Here an additional explanation to dispel this erroneous model was added. Later, the main part deals with constructions of the models based on sound physical principles (no more violation of the first and second laws). Every model examines different variable and demonstrates its effects.

In this part, the examination of the propulsion by the tail is build and explained in a plain English. It is realized that this paper intend mostly to biology major who are not familiar with the added mass concept, the transfer properties and other fluid mechanics concepts (control volume etc). Hence, the presentation is more casual without the formality of mathematics with a minimal dimensional analysis in attempt to make it clear.

NOMENCLATURE

a Shape coefficient
 F Force

h Height of fish tail
 h_0 Initial fish height
 m The (fish) mass
 n Coefficient for the tail’s height
 r Distance from the hinge point
 R Maximum distance from the hinge point
 U fish velocity
 x Distance in straight (movement) direction
 y Distance perpendicular to x

Greek Letters

ω Angular velocity
 ρ density
 θ angle

Subscript

add Added mass/force
 b Body (fish)

Key Words

Transfer Properties, Gravity Centroid, Fish, Propulsion, Dynamics, Added Mass, Vortices

1 Introduction

The movement of fish and other aquatic bodies can be characterized by using relatively simple fluid mechanics principles. As the review of the current prevailing model of rearrangement of von Karman vortex street was shown to be violating the first and sec-

ond laws of the thermodynamics^{1,2}. To summarize the idea, the swimming of the fish or/and aquatic mammal are not propel by the vertices. At best, the von Karman vortex street rearrangement reduces the resistance to the flow. Remember, there is actually no proof that the rearrangement is the cause of the fish propulsion. Lauder at el (2002) showed that vortices appear in the middle of the fish body hence no rearrangement occur. Perhaps, while Lauder and others tried to prove this model, it turn out to be a proof that there is no rearrangement³. The kind of fish that discussed here is propelled by the tail (with minimal assistance of the fins such as tuna etc).

To understand how actually the fish locomotion occurs the added mass and transfer properties have to be explained. The idea of the added mass was introduced because the desire to calculate/measure the time more accurately. The time was measured by using a pendulum in some kind of medium (like air). Because the discrepancy from the expected time and actual time they concluded that there is additional mass. A good description of history of the problem is given in (Bar-Meir 2022c). This introduction of the added mass was done among others by biologist, Charles Darwin. The idea of the added mass was later further developed by very sophisticated techniques. As always, the idea of added mass is conflated other issue, and here with transfer properties and include erroneous elements like turbulence and viscosity etc. Furthermore, as these controversial issues not enough, the location rotation point also is not developed/known, or simply stating, the way it is done today is simply wrong.).

In experiment (Lauder and Drucker 2002) exhibits measurement of the velocity field in the middle of the fish upstream the tail as shown in fig. 1. With this incredible capability and yet the important factors (velocity field in the right locations, downstream and upstream the fish, were not done.) were neglected. That is the possible effect of the tail was neglected. According to the drawing (not sure how they arrived to this conclusion) vortices connect existing in the middle of the fish. This “measurement” immediately conflicts the vortices belief⁴. The researchers

FIGURE 1. Schematic of fish velocity done by taking the core elements from Lauder and Drucker to demonstrate the how the measurements done. Notice the velocity field downstream or upstream were not measured.

attribute the momentum generate to vortex!? For steady state they stated that:

“[t]otal locomotor force is calculated by dividing the fluid momentum of the vortex ring (or rings) shed over a fin beat cycle by the duration of the fin beat.”

The first question that raise in reading this statement: what is the physical principle to attribute the “measured momentum” to the fin beat? This momentum could be there regardless to the fin (It is like hearing CNN). Fluid mechanics requires accounting practice, in-out = change. This idea is very well explained in (Bar-Meir 2021). By the way, as opposed to the claims in the said paper, forces can be measured by velocity field in and out (pressure as well and if you have time on your hands consider gravity.).

With these issues of poor foundations, it is clear why fish locomotion investigation was not able to make a real progress with the exception of improving the numerical techniques. Furthermore, to convert this field to a scientific field, one has to do dimensional analysis utilizing Nusselt/Schmidt technique. At this stage, only the 3rd and 4th parts of these papers series offer a limited analysis.

The current paper series was initiated because the desire to study how the transfer and added mass properties are working for and during the aquatic body movements as opposed to a rigid body like ship, purely for academic interest. While the minimal understanding was gained on the transfer properties, the understanding of the fish propulsion was considerably improved and discussed here.

¹For those who not familiar with these laws, a violation means it does not happen or something is wrong.

²The publication of the first paper in the series brought stream of reactions. These reactions are expected. Some were surprise and not aware that current approach to added mass was wrong (it takes time for the information to travel). Some reactions were very encouraged and some are strange, yet expected, basically the detractors who believe that if they ignore the publication, the ideas will go away. Good luck with that! See what happen on die casting in the same situation (long list of cases of this kind of action). It will be better if either they find how to proof what they are doing is right or accept it. You cannot put the Jenny back to the battle, once the knowledge is out, it will travel to kind of corners. See what happen to the committee (5 individuals) that suggested to ignore Bar-Meir ideas on die casting.

³Like the story Balak and Balaam Joshua 24:9-10.

⁴One can only wonder how they do not see the internal conflict.

2 von Karman Paradox

It was shown that the von Karman vortex street rearrangement belief partially violates first and second laws of thermodynamics. It also was shown that the matching of initial and the continuous of the “releasing” of vortices do not synchronize with the tail movement. At this stage, another explanation that dispels the belief consequence of discussion with users. According to the belief, the two vortices street creating form in the two lines and middle the two added. The distance between the two vertices control this velocity magnitude. When the distance the vortices is very small then the velocities of the two vortices is increase. The velocity of vortex is $U \propto 1/r$. Hence, if the distance between the two vortices increase, the combined velocity decreases as $U \propto 1/r$ as well. Thus, according to the belief, the fish velocity decreases when the angle of the tail movement increase. However, in reality the velocity incenses when the fish swings its tail in a larger angle. This conflict between reality and the model is indication that something is wrong and this conflict is additional reason why the belief should be rejected⁵. The long list issues that the belief has such as large angle conflict with reality, violation of first and second laws, internal conflict (location of the origin of the vortices), lack timing/synchronizing, lack of experimental evidence, and yet it still the prevailing opinion. Even the numerical analysis does not support this belief, and it is not because of deficiency in attempts to proof it. At this stage, this belief moved to the realm super natural and/or political where people whose career depends on this belief will protect it.

3 The Added Mass Properties

The added mass occurs because liquid (water) is displaced by fish movement (the location where the fish was earlier). If fish accelerates, the water is accelerating as well but to a different direction (yet the force is the same direction! (Bar-Meir 2022c)). The force is required to accelerate the fish with water mass. The value of the added mass can be obtained either by theoretical calculations (not so easy) or by experiments. Notice that if no acceleration exist, then there is no added force (no added mass). Hence, no added mass present. The violation of this statement is common, that almost all the numerical papers dealing with the these kind issues simply ignores this fact (actually no paper was found that this point seriously considered).

Any body has only a single added mass which is depends on the acceleration direction. The added mass (added force) can be broken into components in each three arbitrary directions (per your choice of the coordinate system.). It is common to divide

⁵Recently, in a discussion about Free Will (Bar-Meir 2022b) the question was raised; do people attempting to ignore the progress are doing it as a Free Will or not. It seems that it is an example of Free Will because they choose to do it even though they are claiming that they do not do it.

the acceleration (added mass) by the body velocity which yields matrix of 3×3 (division of vector by a vector yield 9 terms). These 9 terms can be used to calculate the added mass in the reverse process. The equations of the terms that can be used and they should be based on the acceleration and not the velocity.

4 Rigid Tail Model

The transfer properties are associated with the fish relative velocity. In current paper, they disguised as a physical process. The regular transfer properties are a function of the fish geometry and its orientation. It is assumed the tail rotation is at constant angular velocity. Consider a body shown in fig. 2. This body represents a simplified schematic of a fish when the tail rotating towards the zero angle point.

FIGURE 2. Schematic of fish tail rotating toward the center 0° with rigid body only one hinge point. The thickness is exaggerated (not realistic) to make point of the difference between front and back. Notice that h is into the page.

The velocity at a distance r from the hinge is $U = r\omega$. A liquid hit the front surface and Bernoulli equation states that the whole kinetic energy should converted into the pressure (if no energy loss occurs and ignore the gravity effect). In the frame of the reference sitting on front of the tail, the water is flowing into tail. In this case, as a first approximation, it is assumed that no energy is lost and hence,

$$\Delta P = \frac{\rho U r^2}{2} \quad (1)$$

In writing eq. (1) several implicit assumptions were made such as pseudo quasi static situation exist, no edge effects, etc. The total force acting on the tail can be obtained by the integration while substituting eq. (1) as

$$F = \int_0^R \Delta P dA = \int_0^R \frac{\rho (\omega r)^2}{2} \overbrace{h(r) dr}^{dA} \quad (2)$$

For a constant tail height $h = \text{constnat}$ (not realistic) the integra-

tion yields

$$F = \frac{\rho \omega^2 h R^3}{6} \quad (3)$$

Or rearranging eq. (3) to a dimensional form yields

$$\frac{F}{h \rho R^3 \omega^2} = \frac{1}{6} \quad (4)$$

On the other side of the tail (back), the situation is a bit more complicate and two extreme cases are provided to bound the solution. The first case: the pressure is the same as in the surroundings. The second case: the pressure reduction (the reverse of the front) is the same as the pressure addition on the other side. Yet, it can be noticed the other side of the area is slightly different. Depending on the fish, the area can be determined. At this stage it is assumed to be identical to the “front” side. The maximum force can be attained is double the one front side is used and on the other boarder is only the front provides force as

$$\frac{\rho \omega^2 h R^3}{6} < F < \frac{\rho \omega^2 h R^3}{3} \quad (5)$$

The reason the solution is bounded and not found directly due to confidence in the energy lost assumption for the back side. While the front side of the tail, the lost is minimal at the back side the flow is less arranged (turbulence) that there is a greater lost. The extend of the lost should be investigated experimentally.

The force is perpendicular to the tail front side is angle to the direction of the fish swimming. The actual force is propelling the fish⁶ forward

$$F_{forward} = F \sin \theta \quad (6)$$

Thus the maximum force appear when the tail is at maximum range.

This results is astonishing, the dimensionless force is a constant. This information provides a rule of thumb for the acceleration of the fish or the resistance (drag) to the fish flow. For example, given fish data, knowing the angular speed of the fish’s tail and given data such as tail length, average height, tail length

provides the acceleration as

$$a \sim \frac{F \sin \theta}{m_b + m_{add}} \sim \frac{\rho \omega^2 h R^3 \sin \theta}{6(m_b + m_{add})} \quad (7)$$

This formula provides some inside about the relationship between the different elements and the fish velocity.

The force acting perpendicular to the path is $F \cos \theta$. Notice that this force changes the location of the gravity centroid. The general relationship between the fish tail rotation speed was established for a simple case. In the negative angle case (see fig. 3 the blue color) the rigid assumption (only the assumption not the fish) means that forward and backward are canceling each other. The change of the gravity centroid is continuous. Yet, on the back stroke, the force is pushing the gravity centroid in the opposite direction.

FIGURE 3. Schematic of fish tail rotating toward the center in the brown and way from the center in blue.

5 Flex Tail

Now it is the time to check how to increase the accuracy of this equation and other effects such net force etc. The shape of the fish tail is curved and with a different height as a function of radius. In addition, the fish’s tail also has a thickness which differentiates the front and the back. In the simple case analysis, a strong assumption that the hinge is fixed. The calculations of the force should include the movement of the gravity centroid.

The examination of the curve suggests that shape behaves like a parabola because of issues of strength of material. This topic out of scope: one) bending is a solid mechanics two) lack of knowledge of fish structure. While this profile is only a preliminary suggestion, it can provide some inside into the effect of the curve has on the force and direction of the resulting force. The assumption of constant height is employed to simplify the calculations and isolate the curve effects.

At this stage the function of $\theta = f(r)$ is a single value function. That is, for every r there is a single value of θ . In formulating the problem this fashion, the actual shape is abstracted

⁶In the first part there was a mistake in the statement in regard to it.

FIGURE 4. Shape of flex tail describing the dimensions used in this integral model.

and removed to later treatment. In this approach the semi-steady state is assumed (implicitly also in the previous case as well.). Of course, this model can be improved yet this simplistic approach provides the core parameters. The only interesting fact is the two components (θ and radius) don't have negative value in the integration. The propelling force is

$$F_p = \frac{\rho}{2} \int_0^R (\omega r)^2 \sin(\theta) h(r) dr \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) is the most general form before the movement of the gravity centroid movements are taken into account. The general shape of the parabola is $y = ax^2$ where a is the shape coefficient and y is the "height" of the local tail as shown in fig. 4 and x is distance from the hinge point in the direction of the fish movement. Notice the "height" refers to the front surface of the tail into the page. The Pythagorean relationship is $r^2 = x^2 + a^2 x^4$. Solving for x and noticing that $a^2 r^2$ is a dimensionless parameter⁷.

$$\frac{x}{r} = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 4a^2 r^2}}{2a^2 r^2} \quad (9)$$

And the angle is

$$\theta = \sin^{-1} \frac{x}{r} = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 4a^2 r^2}}{2a^2 r^2} \right) \quad (10)$$

These equations are the relationship between the geometrical parameters. Substituting eq. (10) into eq. (8) and taking height (of the tail) as constant yields

$$\frac{2F_p}{\rho \omega^2 h} = \int_0^R r^2 \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 4a^2 r^2}}{2a^2 r^2} \right) dr \quad (11)$$

⁷Sorry using a bit jargon here. It is recommended to read the dimensional analysis in (Bar-Meir 2021)

Integrating eq. (11) results as

$$\frac{8F_p a^3}{\rho \omega^2 h} = \frac{\operatorname{asinh}(2ar)}{2} + \frac{2ar \sqrt{4a^2 r^2 + 1}}{2} - 2ar \Big|_0^R \quad (12)$$

The result of eq. (12) is

$$\frac{8F_p a^3}{\rho \omega^2 h} = \frac{\operatorname{asinh}(2aR)}{2} + \frac{2aR \sqrt{4a^2 R^2 + 1}}{2} - 2aR \quad (13)$$

As oppose the rigid case with constant value for positive angle and negative for negative angle, the flex tail (force) is positive value also for negative angle. When the tail is flexible, the force is exponential and also positive for negative angle. For very small R this equation can be reduced (not physical but those who like mathematics)

$$\frac{8F_p a^3}{\rho \omega^2 h} \sim \frac{\operatorname{asinh}(2aR)}{2} \sim aR \quad (14)$$

Again it is not a constant as it was for the rigid tail. This result is a profound effect for the positive angle. Furthermore, for the negative angle, the results are still positive, astonishing. This analysis demonstrates that a research done by Read et al (2003) is a prime example of how not to do realistic research.

FIGURE 5. Results of the force for flex and rigid tail. Notice, the red line represent the total force not the component in the direction in the flow.

5.1 The Height Change

The effect height change is expressed in eq. (2) but was not solved yet. Most tails that have been observed are showing increase with the height (the analysis did not show even a single tail that height decreased with the radius initially). The literature review on this issue demonstrates how empty the research was up to today (2022)⁸.

From engineering point of view, the fish tail (caudal fin) has several “design” possibilities. Generally speaking, the tail can be flat or with a cut in the “V” shape like shark, tuna (see fig. 6). Some tails are more rounded. In this discussion, issue like evolution, which tail are better for what purpose are left to biologists to sort out. Here, it is merely examination of what happen to the propelling force when the tail increases.

FIGURE 6. Shark tail showing the characteristics. The tail has a vee shape cut while other have flat tail. The height increases but later it is reduced because the upper part is longer.

Clearly, the tail height starts from some value. The most common tails (this part should be done by biologists.) is assumed a linear increase of the tail such as

$$h(r) = h_0 + nr \quad (15)$$

where n is the tail linear coefficient and it is assumed to be positive but it does not have to be so. The force is

$$F = \int_0^R \frac{\rho (\omega r)^2}{2} (h_0 + nr) dr \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) can be modify as

$$\frac{2F}{\rho \omega^2} = \int_0^R r^2 (h_0 + nr) dr \quad (17)$$

⁸If you aware any research of real value please make this author aware of it.

The integration of eq. (17) provides

$$\frac{2F}{\rho \omega^2} = \frac{R^3 h_0}{3} + \frac{nR^4}{4} \quad (18)$$

The results are same as the rigid case plus a new term that is much stronger (higher power). The small amount increase in the fish tail height can be more significant than the whole tail without it. This information might be important to evolutionary biologist on the issue why tail developed in a certain way.

6 Results and Discussion

Several points were made here in regard the old models and current state in fish propulsion understanding. First it has to be emphasized that the rearrangement of von Karman vortex street at maximum reduces the fish resistance (by recovering some energy) but it does not propel the aquatic creature. The rigid model was build to provide a minimum standard. This provide a rule of thumb as guessing that the fish acceleration (or drag) from a known tail geometry, and angular velocity of the tail. The model of flex tail and expanding tail were examined. It was shown the flex tail is exponentially more powerful as compared to the rigid tail. The linear increase tail shows also increase in the force and it is change from R^3 to R^4 . The specific of every fish can be later study to improve the accuracy of the model.

Concluding Remarks

Obviously this paper is different from all the papers published earlier in this area because the paper proposed totally new idea(s) and alleged that old model, at least in part, violates the first and second law of thermodynamics. Thus, if you believe that the ideas in this paper are correct, you should change the way you deal with the fish propulsion. If you do not believe in these ideas, you are welcome to criticize the paper, all remarks on paper/email are appreciated. This section is the second part of the install in this series. Currently, the third and fourth parts are in a draft form and may or may not published and join many unpublished papers of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this

manuscript.

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